

Information sheet 1.08

Physical treatments on consignments or during processing

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment

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A. Description of the RRO

This information sheet deals with physical treatments other than heat and cold treatments (information sheet 1.14). The removal of plants or plant parts from the field is covered by the information sheet 1.12 Roguing and pruning.

ISPM 28 (2007) describes modalities for the evaluation and the approval of different categories of methods for the control of regulated pests, including mechanical, irradiation and other physical treatments.

Methods based on physical principles (other than temperature) may be used in order to kill, to prevent development, to reduce viability, fertility or populations of pests that are present on/in plants or plant parts or plant products. This is the case for instance of irradiation/ionisation (Annexes PT1-PT14 and PT19 of ISPM 28). Other methods allow decreasing pest populations that are present on consignments, on the surface of plants, parts of plants or plant products, or that are associated with plant residues, dust, soil... This is the case for washing, brushing or other mechanical cleaning methods.

It is also possible to rely on methods to remove infected/infested plants, plant parts or plant products from consignments (sorting, grading) or to eliminate plant parts or other material at risk (debarking, leaves removal, soil or growing medium removal...). Such methods reduce the pest load of plants or plant products.

Finally, it may be noted that processing of plants or plant products may destroy pests (e.g. sawing is likely to kill most wood-borers pests of a certain size). However this is not covered in this information sheet.

Table 1. Pests that can be affected by physical methods other than temperature applied on consignments or during processing.

Plant pests	RROs			
	irradiation / ionisation	washing, brushing and other mechanical cleaning methods	sorting and grading	removal of plant parts likely to be associated with the pest
insects, mites	x	x	x	x
fungi	x	x	x	x
bacteria	x	x	x	x
nematodes	x	x	x	x
virus, virus like organisms			x	

Table 2. Material that can be subjected to physical methods other than temperature on consignments or during processing.

Plants or plant parts	RROs			removal of plant parts likely to be associated with the pest
	irradiation / ionisation	washing, brushing and other mechanical cleaning methods	sorting and grading	
plants for planting		x	x	x
Bulbs, corms, tubers for planting		x	x	x
seeds		x	x	
plant material for food / feed	x	x	x	x
plant parts for ornamental uses (cut flowers, leaves...)			x	x
wood, packaging material	x		x	x
growing media, soil	x			x

B. Risk factors

Entry

The relevant pathways are the trade of plants or plant parts for planting (including seeds), for food and feed, for other uses (ornamental uses, industrial uses...) and packaging material.

The use of the RROs reduces the likelihood of the association of the pest in consignments ready to be exported by acting either on the survival of the pest in the consignments (removal of parts where the pest is located or survives), either on the pest load (removal of plants or plant parts where the pest is). It therefore reduces the global pest load of consignments and limits the multiplication of pests during transport.

The use of the RROs reduces the likelihood of the pest escaping other existing management procedures considering that detection during inspections (field, packing house, entry point) may be poorly effective.

Establishment

The use of the RROs can minimise pest populations so that they are kept below the level that is required for successful establishment.

Spread

The use of the RROs may reduce the probability of association of pests with consignments in a similar way as for entry.

Impact when pests are established in the country of destination

The considered RROs mainly aim to limit the probability of entry and establishment of pests. Where the pest is already present in the PRA area, these measures may reduce the pest inoculum and allow the pest population to be kept under a value leading to acceptable impact, especially when combined with other RROs.

Table 3. Nodes for the application of RROs.

Points where measures may be effective	RROs			
	Irradiation / ionisation	washing, brushing and other mechanical cleaning methods	sorting and grading	removal of plant parts likely to be associated with the pest
pre-harvest				X
harvest		X	X	X
post-harvest	X	X	X	X
export		X	X	X
transport				
destination	X	X	X	
establishment				
spread			X	X
impacts		X	X	

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

Washing, brushing, other mechanical cleaning methods as well as sorting and grading are effective only for pests located outside the plant material or that show external symptoms. Irradiation and ionisation are effective even for pests that are inside plant material and cause no observable external symptoms. Those methods cannot be used for all kind of plant products and against all kind of pests.

C.1. Irradiation or ionisation

Such treatments rely on exposure to gamma-rays, x-rays or accelerated electrons. Effectiveness depends on dosage and duration of exposure, but also on conditions during exposure (temperature, humidity, ventilation, composition of the atmosphere). The appropriate level of treatment (dose...) should be applied on the entire consignment. Minimum dose range tables are available for a set of pests (ISPM 18) and in ISPM 15 for wood packaging material.

As the objective is not always to kill pests but for instance to make them sterile (Hallman, 2000), the presence of remaining living pests at the end of a treatment does not necessarily indicate a failure.

Technical data that are necessary to determine the appropriate dose to be delivered are not available for all kinds of plant material and all pests. The International Database on Insect Disinfestation and Sterilization (IDIDAS, 2013) provides information on the doses of radiation to be used against some pests of crops (mites and insects) for disinfestation or sterilization.

Technical information assisting in the use of these methods of pest control is also available from the Joint FAO/IAEA programme on Nuclear Techniques in Food and Agriculture.

C.2. Washing, brushing and other mechanical cleaning methods

The effectiveness of washing depends on water temperature, additives (detergents, sanitization compounds...), duration, water pressure, stirring conditions.

The effectiveness of other methods is related to their intensity, the duration and the appropriate removal of dust during the treatment. The humidity of the elements to be removed as well as their adherence are also key factors that may alter the effectiveness of the RRO.

The dirtier consignments are, the more difficult it is to clean them and therefore to get rid of pests.

C.3. Sorting and grading

The effectiveness of sorting and grading varies according to pests, their phenological stage and the symptoms they cause, some being easily recognised while others can be hardly seen. It can also differ according to plant material considered (e.g. some varieties may be more difficult to sort or grade because of colours, shape...)

When sorting or grading operations are performed by people, training and working conditions are crucial to ensure an appropriate effectiveness of the treatment.

C.4. Removal of plant parts or of other parts at risk

The effectiveness of removal of plant parts likely to be associated with the pest (for instance leaves, fruit, calyx) varies according to pests, plant species and the commodity traded. All plant parts at risk shall be removed without any exception, and shall not remain associated with the consignment (on the surface of pots for potted plants for instance).

For wood, several options are possible: debarking or squaring (so as to remove the round surface). To choose the relevant options, the biology of the pest should be taken into account (e.g. whether the pest develops in the bark, in the sapwood). Debarking may affect the quality of the wood depending on wood species. The effectiveness of debarking may be limited for wood plant varieties / species, or lots, that do not have broad enough surfaces or when the trunk surface is not smooth. It should be noted that debarked wood is not necessarily bark-free (see ISPM 5 for definitions).

The effectiveness of the removal of soil or growing medium depends on soil type (sandy, muddy, clayey...) and humidity, on root density and on plant species, and on plant pests.

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

Relevant examples for this group of RROs are included in Annexes of the Council Directive 2000/29/EC¹ on protective measures against the introduction and spread into the European Union territory of organisms harmful to plants or plant products.

Annex IV, part a, section I defines the special requirements for the introduction and movement of plants, plant products and other objects originating outside the Union. In this Annex, point 43 establishes specific requirements for naturally or artificially dwarfed plants intended for planting including the removal of the original growing medium by shaking and washing them with clean water.

In the same Annex, point 2.3 lists two options for the import of wood of *Fraxinus* L., *Juglans ailantifolia* Carr., *Juglans mandshurica* Maxim., *Ulmus davidiana* Planch. and *Pterocarya rhoifolia* Siebold & Zucc., both considered as equivalent from a phytosanitary point of view to the requirement of consignment originating in an area recognised as being free from *Agrilus planipennis* Fairmaire (option (a)). The first alternative option (b) provides for debarking and removing of at least 2.5 cm of the outer sapwood in an authorised and supervised facility; the other alternative option (c) requires the treatment by ionizing irradiation to achieve a minimum absorbed dose of 1 kGy throughout the wood.

¹ Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8 May 2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organism harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Table 4. Potential limitations to the practical application of RROs.

Limits to be considered regarding applicability	RROs			removal of plant parts likely to be associated with the pest
	irradiation / ionisation	washing, brushing and other mechanical cleaning methods	sorting and grading	
Regulatory limitations	x ¹			
Technical difficulties	x ²	x	x	x
Environmental limitations				
Social or ethical aspects	x ³			
Potential side effects				x
Economic considerations	x ⁴			x

¹ Ionisation / irradiation shall be authorised in the EU for the intended use. The presence of live quarantine pests, even if sterile may not be accepted.

² Require dedicated facilities or equipment. Not applicable to all types of consignments

³ Social reluctance for ionisation processes, especially for food commodities.

⁴ Extra costs.

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

Application of pesticides on plants, plant parts or plant products may lead to similar effects by reducing the prevalence of pests, which may therefore no more need irradiation or ionisation. It may also make mechanical cleaning or sorting / grading processes useless.

Growing plants in particular conditions (e.g. potatoes in sandy soils) may lead to productions that do not require any washing or brushing steps during packaging operations.

Heat or cold treatments of consignments may also lead to effects similar to irradiation or ionisation, for certain pests.

Nevertheless, there is no general rule; effectiveness of those RROs highly depends on plant products, associated pests and prevalence of those pests in the field of origin.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

Some of those physical treatments of consignments or during processing can be stand-alone measures (e.g. irradiation).

Nevertheless, most of those RROs are most often required in combination with other RROs (application of pesticides in fields, heat or cold treatment of consignments...), that are additional measures that may make physical treatment of the consignments more effective (reduction of pest load, reduction of viability, elimination of dust...).

After sorting and grading, or washing /brushing, or removal of plant parts or of other parts at risk, appropriate waste management should be applied.

Inspection (based on sampling) should be used to verify this RRO.

G. Conclusions

Synoptic table for the RROs.

Targets	place of application	expected effect	main technical limitations	RROs with similar effects / most often in combination
Irradiation, ionization				
Pest or vector / plants for planting, plant parts for food or feed.	Packaging facilities, transport, points of entry.	Sanitation of consignments to be exported.	Availability of technical data (required dose for a given type of plant product), availability of equipment for treatment.	Heat or cold treatments, pesticides.
Washing, brushing and other mechanical operations				
Pest or vector / plants for planting, plant parts for food or feed.	Packaging facilities.	Reduction of the prevalence of the pest or of its vector in the consignments to be exported or to be planted.	Not adapted to all kind of plant products, availability of suitable equipment, conservation after treatment (impact of humidity and injuries on plant material), not adapted to pests that are inside plant products.	Culture in conditions that lead to surface clean plant products.
Grading and sorting				
Pest / plants for planting, plant parts for food or feed.	Packaging facilities.	Reduction of the prevalence of the pest in the consignments to be exported or to be planted.	Some plant products or varieties may be more difficult to sort or to grade because of colors or shape. Only abnormal plant products (showing symptoms) can be targeted by grading or sorting.	
Removal of plant parts or of other parts at risk				
Pest or vector / plants for planting, plant parts for food, feed or other uses.	Field, packaging facilities	Reduction of the prevalence of the pest in the consignments to be exported or to be planted.	Debarking, and soil or substrate removal require special equipment or adequate manpower, it is not adapted to all plants or plant materials	

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